

PRESSURE INFLUENCE DURING CURING ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF EPOXY RESIN COMPOSITES AT HIGH STRAIN RATES

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Keywords: CFRP, Epoxy, Pressure Dependency, Crash Behavior, Fracture Toughness

ABSTRACT

Fibre reinforced plastics are used in many applications due to their good strength to weight ratio. Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) with epoxy resin matrix are often used in automotive applications. The crash behaviour and thus the behaviour of the composite at high strain rates is of great importance for this application. [1] Composites are produced in automatable processes such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) or in autoclave processes with prepregs, where the process pressures are increased. [2] The influence of the process pressure on the curing behaviour and therefore on the material properties has, however, only been investigated to a limited extent in the literature [3]. The aim of this work is to investigate if even a small pressure difference of 5 bar, which is common in the RTM process, leads to changes in material properties under high strain rates as occurring in the crash case in automotive engineering. Izod notched bar impact tests on epoxy resin specimens and tensile tests with high strain rates on CFRP are carried out. The notched bar impact tests show a significant increase of the notched bar impact strength with an increased pressure. The fracture surfaces also differ between the different pressure states. The specimens cured under increased pressure show significantly rougher fracture surfaces, which indicate a changed fracture behavior. During fracture, significantly more energy is absorbed. The tensile tests with a high strain rate show that the pressure influence also occurs in CFRP with fibres. A significantly higher energy absorption during fracture is determined here. This work shows that the process pressure during curing has a significant influence on the behaviour of CFRP under high strain rates. Therefore, it is possible to directly influence the properties under high strain rates by process parameters in the RTM process without adding viscosity increasing additives.

1 INTRODUCTION

The crash behaviour of CFRP is of great importance, for example, in the automotive industry. High strain rates occur during crashes. To reduce the mass, CFRP with epoxy resin as matrix material are often used in automotive applications. [1] The impact strength and therefore the crash behaviour of CFRP components can be improved on the one hand by selecting the type of fibre, e.g. by using aramid fibres, or by modifying the matrix properties. Epoxy resins are widely used in technical applications as matrix material for CFRP due to their good mechanical properties, high thermal resistance and chemical resistance. [4] The good mechanical properties are due to the formation of dense networks. These networks have short chain segments (net chains) between the network nodes. The short net chains restrict the freedom of movement of the chains in the network. Therefore, they can only be stretched slightly and absorb low energy under load. [5] For this reason, epoxy resins show brittle material behaviour. This significantly restricts their use in applications with impact loads [4].

In the literature, methods for increased impact strength are described. These include the addition of elastomers [6, 7], thermoplastics [8, 9], nanoparticles [10, 11] and liquid crystalline polymers [12, 13] or the formation of hyperbranched networks [14-16]. However, these methods are usually associated with a reduction of the mechanical properties. Furthermore, the use of additives makes processing more demanding due to the increased viscosity.

It is described in the literature that epoxy resin can be cured by catalysis with tertiary amines. Long net chains are formed by homopolymerization of the epoxy resin chains. It is shown that by increasing the curing temperature at the beginning of the reaction the homopolymerization can be accelerated and thus longer net chains can be integrated into the amine network. In this network topology, the longer chains interpenetrate each other and form entanglements (physical network nodes). In contrast to chemical network nodes, these physical network nodes can slide against each other under load and dissipate energy through friction. In addition, the longer network chains can be stretched more than short network chains because of their length. With this network topology, the impact strength can be more than doubled by optimized temperature control [17].

In mass production, fibre composites with epoxy resin matrix are produced, e.g. by resin transfer moulding or by autoclave process. In the RTM process, the epoxy resin is injected into a mould under increased pressure. The fibres are impregnated. Low-viscosity epoxy resins are required for this process and the use of viscosity-increasing additives is limited [2]. A typical low viscosity epoxy resin system with tertiary amines is investigated in this paper.

It is assumed that other RTM process parameters also lead to changes in network formation. This changed network can lead to an increase in impact strength and thus increase the strength of endless fiber reinforced plastics at high strain rates. In this paper the process parameter pressure is investigated. For this purpose notched bar impact tests on pure matrix material and tensile tests with high strain rate on specimens with 1 bar and 6 bar are carried out. These pressures are typical for RTM parts in automotive engineering [2].

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Material

Highly reactive resin systems are used in the RTM process to achieve short infiltration times and thus short cycle times [2]. In this work a commercial resin system consisting of epoxy resin CR170 (DGEBA) and hardener CH150-3 from Sika Deutschland GmbH is used. The epoxy resin contains bisphenol-A diglycidyl ether ($\geq 50\%$ to $\leq 100\%$, DGEBA) with a minimum average molecular weight of 700. The hardener is composed of 3-aminomethyl-3,5,5-trimethyl-cyclohexylamine (between 60% and 80%, IPDA) and 2-piperazine-1-ylethylamine (between 25% and 40 %, AEP). The carbon fibres are a woven fabric (FT300B, Toray Industries, Inc., Japan) with a weight of 160 g/m².

2.2 Curing

The curing of the epoxy resin system with and without fibres is based on the RTM process. Two phases are distinguished. In the curing phase, the specimens are cured until they are sufficiently solid to be demoulded. The maximum degree of curing is not yet reached in this phase because this reduces the RTM cycle time. The reaction is then stopped by cooling and the specimens are stored until annealing. In the annealing phase, the epoxy resin system then cures to the maximum degree of curing.

In the curing phase, the epoxy resin system is metered into aluminium moulds using a Conti Flow Vario metering system (Reinhard-Technik GmbH, Germany). For the notched bar impact tests, an aluminium mould consisting of a 4 mm thick base plate and a 4 mm thick mould plate with four notched bar impact specimen cavities is used. The cavities have the geometry of the specimen according to ISO 180B standard [18]. A 4 mm thick rectangular aluminium mould plate with a cavity of 300 mm x 200 mm is used for the tensile tests. The cavity of the notched bar impact test specimens is completely filled with epoxy resin to produce 4 mm thick notched bar impact test specimens. The specimen plates for the tensile tests are manufactured by hand lamination with the same mass of resin. Four layers of woven canvas carbon fibres with the same direction are used and air inclusions are removed after each layer with a ventilation roller. The mould is coated with the silicone-free release

agent ACMOS 82-2405 (Acmos Chemie KG, Germany) before each sample production. Subsequently, the mould with the epoxy resin system is placed in a pressure cell located in a furnace (Heraeus Holding GmbH, Germany). The pressure cell is made of steel and has a wall thickness of at least 15 mm. The furnace is regulated to the desired process temperature for at least 4 hours before sample production to ensure that the pressure cell has reached the process temperature. The samples are cured at 1 bar (atmospheric pressure) or 6 bar. The pressure is set by a compressed air supply. From metering to curing in the pressure cell, a maximum of 90 s is allowed for the impact test specimens and a maximum of 300 s is allowed for the tensile test specimen plates. After curing, the specimens are cooled down in a freezer to $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 minutes and then demoulded. After demoulding, the specimens are stored in the freezer at $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until annealing. To avoid possible influence of humidity, the specimens are packed in aluminium foil during cooling and subsequent storage and additionally stored in a PE bag. The maximum storage time until annealing is 24 hours.

The annealing phase is identical for all specimen types. All specimens in a test series are annealed at the same time in the furnace at $130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 minutes. This ensures that the temperature does not differ between the samples during annealing. After annealing, the samples are stored in a climatic room until testing in a standard climate ($23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 50% r.H.).

2.3 Notched bar impact test

The aim of this test series is to investigate the influence of pressure during the curing phase on the notched bar impact strength of the matrix material. 11 specimens with 1 bar curing pressure and 12 specimens with 6 bar curing pressure are investigated. The test is carried out with a pendulum hammer impact tester type 5101 (Zwick, Germany). The pendulum length is 390 mm and the pendulum energy 1 J. The specimens are clamped so that the impact mechanism hits the specimen on the notch side. The Izod notched bar impact strength is determined according to ISO standard and the standard errors are given [18].

After the test, the fracture surfaces are examined with a DSX500 light microscope (Olympus, Japan).

2.4 Tensile test

The aim of this test series is to investigate the influence of pressure on the mechanical behavior of CFRP. For a maximum matrix influence, a fiber orientation of $\pm 45^{\circ}$ degrees is realized in all four layers [19]. Rectangular tensile specimens (50 mm x 10 mm) are milled from the specimen plates.

The test is performed with an ElectroPuls E10000 (Instron GmbH, Germany) with a test speed of 0.5 m/s. This corresponds to a strain rate of 50 s^{-1} . The scanning rate during the test is 10 kHz, whereby about 150 measuring points are recorded during the tests. The strain is determined by digital image correlation. The specimens are coated with a speckle pattern and the test is recorded with Fastcam Mini UX100 high-speed cameras (Photron, USA). The strain evaluation is performed with the image correlation software Istra 4D (Dantec Dynamics A/S, Denmark) at a 10 mm gauge length.

The stress-strain behaviour, the Young's modulus, the elongation at break and the stress at break are evaluated.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Notched bar impact test

Figure 1 shows the results of the Izod notched bar impact strength. For the 1 bar samples an Izod notched impact strength of $2.27 \pm 0.3\text{ KJ/m}^2$ is measured. In the literature, an Izod notched bar impact strength of converted $2.62 \pm 0.22\text{ KJ/m}^2$ is determined for a comparable epoxy resin consisting 100% of the main component of the epoxy resin system used in this study [20]. These results agree with the literature in the range of standard deviation. The samples cured at 6 bar show an increase in Izod notched impact strength of 23.3% compared to the 1 bar samples.

Figure 1: Measured izod notched bar impact strength at 1 bar and 6 bar specimens

Figure 2 shows the fracture surface of a representative 1 bar sample. The notch of the specimen can be seen in the lower part of the figure. This side of the specimen is hit with the impact hammer and the crack therefore begins at the ground of the notch. In the left area the beginning of the crack can be seen. A rough fracture surface is visible in this area. The remaining fracture surface, which corresponds to about 75% of the total fracture surface, is smooth. The smooth fracture surface is an indicator of brittle fracture behaviour with little energy absorption.

Figure 2: smooth fracture surface of a 1 bar specimen.

In contrast to the 1 bar samples, the 6 bar samples have rough fracture surfaces. Figure 3 shows the fracture surface of a representative 6 bar sample. The rough surface with grooves indicates a significantly changed fracture behavior with higher energy absorption. The characteristics of the fracture surfaces on the microscopy images correlate with the Izod notched impact strengths shown in Figure 1.

Figure 3: rough fracture surface of a 6 bar specimen.

3.2 Tensile test

The results of the Izod notched bar impact tests on epoxy resin without carbon fibers suggest a pressure influence during curing on the mechanical properties at high elongation rates, also for CFRP. The aim of the tensile tests performed is to investigate whether this effect also has a significant influence on the mechanical properties in the composite with carbon fibres.

Figure 4 shows the stress-strain characteristic of the tensile tests with a nominal strain rate of 50 m^{-1} . The 6 bar specimens have a 15.3% higher Young's modulus (see Table 1). The breaking stress is increased by 14.5% compared to the 1 bar specimens. The strain at break is 15.3% lower for 6 bar specimens than for 1 bar specimens. The energy absorbed at break is increased for the 6 bar specimens compared to the 1 bar specimens.

Figure 4: Stress-strain diagram of 1 bar and 6 bar specimens

Pressure (Bar)	Young's modulus (MPa)	stress at break (MPa)	strain at break (-)
1	3225.89 ± 23.57	175.11 ± 2.11	0.166 ± 0.009
6	3808.76 ± 52.29	200.58 ± 8.16	0.144 ± 0.012

Table 1: Mechanical properties at 1 bar and 6 bar

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The behaviour of CFRP under high strain rates is of great importance in many applications such as automotive parts (crash behaviour) or sports equipment. Epoxy resin systems are often used as matrix materials due to their high mechanical and thermal stability. Due to their chemical network, epoxy resins exhibit brittle fracture behavior and their use in applications with high strain rates is challenging. An increase in the impact strength of the epoxy resin can be achieved, for example, by using additives. CFRP can be produced economically using the autoclave process or resin transfer moulding. Low viscosity resins are required for the RTM process. For this reason, increasing the impact strength of the epoxy resin system with additives, which usually increase the viscosity, is only possible to a limited extent. In the RTM process, temperature and pressure can be varied as process parameters. The literature shows that temperature control can increase the impact strength of epoxy resins [17]. In this study the influence of the process parameter pressure on the impact strength of

epoxy resin and CFRP with epoxy resin matrix is investigated. The curing process is modelled following the RTM process. The curing takes place in a curing phase at 1 bar and 6 bar followed by an annealing phase at 1 bar pressure. This two-part curing is typical for the RTM process and leads to a shorter cycle time and an increase in the economic efficiency of the process.

The Izod notched bar impact tests carried out in this study show an increase in the impact strength of the matrix of 23.3% at 5 bar pressure increase. The analysis of the fracture surfaces shows a clearly changed fracture behaviour. The 1 bar specimens show a predominantly brittle fracture with a smooth fracture surface and the 6 bar specimens show a ductile fracture with a rough fracture surface. The fracture pattern of the 6 bar specimens indicates increased energy absorption during the fracture and correlates with the specific notched impact strengths. A significant pressure influence on the epoxy resin matrix during curing is observed. An increase of the curing pressure by 5 bar therefore significantly increases the impact strength of CFRP.

The increase in the impact strength of the matrix leads to an increase in the breaking stress and the Young's modulus in tensile tests with high strain rates on CFRP. It is observed that the absorbed energy of the 6 bar specimens is significantly increased compared to the 1 bar specimens.

The results of this work suggest that the impact strength and behavior at high strain rates of CFRP in the RTM process can be optimized with pressure control. Further work should investigate if this effect can be used in real RTM components. For example, crash optimized components can be manufactured cost-effectively in the automotive industry using the pressure influences.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the German National Science Foundation (DFG).

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